

100 c.c. of alcohol containing sufficient ferrous sulphate to decompose persulphate; excess ammonia was added and the mercaptan was amperometrically titrated with standard silver nitrate solution (Kolthoff and Harris, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1946, 18, 161). The chain-transfer constant (C) was calculated with the formula of Mayo,

$$\frac{d \ln(\text{RSH})}{d \ln(M)} = C$$

where RSH designates the mercaptan and M, the monomer.

The rate of polymerisation was found to be 2.1% per hour and it was the same in absence of mercaptan in the above recipe. This is expected from the mechanism of chain transfer. C was found as 19.3; the value found by Kolthoff *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) was 23 with redox initiator. The difference may be due to some reaction of mercaptan with the redox initiator. The thermal decomposition of persulphate is so low that it cannot account for even a very small fraction of disappearance of mercaptan. There is not the slightest doubt about chain-transfer mechanism of mercaptan at 50° with persulphate as initiator; the identical value of the chain-transfer constant with the same initiator at 5° definitely proves the same mechanism of mercaptan at that temperature.

The authors express their thanks to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research for granting a Research Assitanship to one of them (K.L.M.).

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
JADAVPUR UNIVERSITY,
CALCUTTA.

Received February 13, 1957.

[*Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, Vol. 34, No. 5, 1957]

ON THE PREPARATION OF 4-METHYLCINNOLINE

BY A. B. LAL

The synthesis of 4-methylcinnoline has been described in the literature (Jacobs *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1310; Simpson and Atkinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 808). In connection with another work, larger quantities of this substance were required. Attempts to prepare it by the methods already described resulted in small yields. Jacobs' method (*loc. cit.*) of dehydrating the tertiary alcohol (*o*-aminophenyldimethyl carbinol) with iodine in boiling toluene did not prove successful. The preparation of the tertiary alcohol and its subsequent dehydration, however, proceeded smoothly according to the method described by Simpson *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). The latter authors, however, diazotised and cyclised the crude *o*-isopropenylaniline to 4-methylcinnoline. Attempt to repeat this furnished a deep green residue (as described by Simpson *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) but on extracting it with petroleum ether only a red oil was obtained, which could be crystallised with difficulty, affording a small quantity of 4-methylcinnoline. When this oil was distilled under reduced pressure, 4-methylcinnoline was obtained in a low yield (b.p. 146-50°/10 mm).

It was therefore concluded that the purification of the *o*-isopropenylaniline was necessary, and accordingly the crude product was distilled (b.p. 115-20°/20 mm; Jacobs *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, b.p. 83.5° to 87.5°/1-2 mm). This was characterised by its hydrochloride, m.p. 171-73° (Jacobs *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, record, m.p. 163-68.5°) and picrate, m.p. 149-50° (flat needles from alcohol).

The pure *o*-isopropenylaniline (23 g.) was dissolved in hydrochloric acid (200 c.c., 2*N*) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (40 c.c.) was then added. A small amount of undissolved oil floating on the surface was extracted with ether (100 c.c.). The solution was cooled to 2° and sodium nitrite (11 g.) added slowly (2 hours) with stirring. The green solution, thus obtained, was again extracted with ether (100 c.c.) to remove a small quantity of a red oil. The solution was then heated up to 60° (the colour changed to red) and allowed to stand for two days at room temperature. It was neutralised with sodium carbonate (slight excess) and the yellow oil liberated was extracted with ether (thrice, 100 c.c. each), dried (anhydrous sodium carbonate) and the ether removed. This gave a brown oil which crystallised into rosettes on cooling (10.5 g.). A further quantity of green oil separated (from the solution, which had been neutralised with sodium carbonate) on addition of a concentrated solution of NaOH. This was also worked up as above and furnished light green rosettes (11 g.). Total yield 86%. Crystallisation from petroleum ether (60°-80°, charcoal) furnished yellowish white needles, m.p. 73-74° in 17.5 g. yield (75%). (Jacobs *et al.*, 72.5-74° and Simpson *et al.*, 74-75°).

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY
PATNA UNIVERSITY,
PATNA-6.

Received March 6, 1957.